

NovaT2A : PMSI agentic AI evaluation on fictitious hospital stays with adjudicated expert review

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Abstract

Background: Hospital activity-based payment depends on accurate PMSI coding. Large language model assisted coding systems may identify valid diagnoses or procedures that are missed by initial human coding, but evaluation against a single human gold standard may be misleading when expert coders legitimately disagree.

Objective: To evaluate the comparative performance, assisted validated added value, and expert-relative acceptability of NovaT2A on a corpus of fictitious hospital stays.

Methods: We conducted a comparative methodological performance study on 42 deduplicated fictitious stays processed by the NovaT2A version dated 1 May 2026. Four experts independently performed blinded primary coding. NovaT2A proposals, including final declared codes and additional system-generated candidate codes, were subsequently reviewed code by code by the same four-expert panel and adjudicated. The primary valuation design measured assisted added value rather than autonomous AI performance: the comparator was the maximum groupable valuation obtained from the four independent human primocodings when available, and the intervention valuation was this selected human baseline augmented with NovaT2A codes adjudicated valid by expert review. When no primary coding could be grouped, a review-informed human baseline was inferred from codes adjudicated valid by the expert panel. Exhaustivity was assessed against the validated superset produced by review and adjudication. The protocol-specified primary judgment criterion was assisted validated net valuation gain per stay. Secondary outcomes included strict precision among evaluable NovaT2A proposals, hallucination rate, semantic recall over the validated code superset, detection ratio, and expert-relative evaluation using Rank from References [1].

Results: The final analysis included 42 stays, 478 NovaT2A proposals, and 462 evaluable proposals. Assisted validated net valuation gain was measured for all 42 stays. The mean gain of the best groupable human baseline plus validated NovaT2A codes versus the same human baseline alone was 857.60 euros per stay (95% CI, 416.32 to 1,388.49), corresponding to a 28.2% relative increase over the human baseline (95% CI, 12.2% to 49.4%) and meeting the protocol threshold of a lower confidence bound above 0 euros. Strict precision was 64.9% (300/462; 95% CI, 60.5% to 69.1%), below the pre-specified secondary performance threshold of 85% with a lower 95% CI bound above 75%. The hallucination rate among evaluable proposals was 1.5% (7/462). NovaT2A semantic recall over the validated code superset was 80.8% (316/391), compared with 28.9% (113/391) for the human consensus. In RFR analysis, NovaT2A had a global normalized rank of 0.915 (95% CI, 0.861 to 0.959), corresponding to a consensus-proximity percentile of 8.5%.

Conclusions: On this fictitious PMSI corpus, NovaT2A identified many adjudicated valid codes beyond the human consensus, leading to higher semantic superset recall and a positive assisted valuation gain when validated NovaT2A codes were added to the best groupable human baseline. This was not an AI-alone versus human valuation comparison. The primary valuation threshold was met, but the pattern of coding remained globally distant from the human expert panel in RFR analysis. The results support a coder-in-the-loop interpretation: NovaT2A can be evaluated as an exhaustivity and proposal-generation system, while strict expert review remains necessary for compliance-sensitive use.

Keywords: PMSI; hospital coding; clinical text; large language models; human annotation; Rank from References; activity-based payment.

Graphical Abstract

1 Introduction

1.1 Clinical and operational context

Hospital clinical coding converts narrative clinical documentation into standardized diagnosis and procedure codes used for case-mix description, epidemiology, quality monitoring, hospital management, and reimbursement. In France, the Programme de medicalisation des systemes d'information (PMSI) is the operational basis for activity-based payment in acute care. PMSI coding requires not only identifying conditions and procedures, but also assigning their role in the stay, including principal diagnosis, related diagnosis, associated diagnoses, and CCAM procedures. These choices can affect grouping, tariff valuation, and downstream administrative interpretation.

The economic scale of this coding environment is substantial. In the latest DREES health accounts, French current health expenditure in the international sense reached 333 billion euros in 2024, corresponding to 11.4% of gross domestic product; the consumption of care and medical goods reached 255 billion euros; hospital care accounted for 120.7 billion euros, or 47% of that consumption; and public administrations financed 202 billion euros, or 79.4% of the consumption of care and medical goods [2]. Within acute-care hospital financing, ATIH describes

MCO stay financing as being based on homogeneous patient groups and, in most cases, associated homogeneous-stay tariffs [3]. The most recent Cour des comptes audit dedicated to T2A reported that activity-based tariffs represented 51.84 billion euros in 2021, equal to 71% of the MCO expenditure objective and 54% of the ONDAM sub-objective for health establishments; it also reported 42.47 billion euros strictly devoted to stay tariffs in 2019 [4]. These figures place coding-sensitive activity-based financing at a tens-of-billions annual scale. A systematic 1% shift on a 50 billion euro activity-based envelope would correspond to approximately 0.5 billion euros, which explains why small stay-level valuation differences can matter at national scale.

Clinical coding is therefore a high-stakes cognitive task. Coders must review heterogeneous documentation, abstract relevant clinical facts, apply regularly updated coding rules, and select codes at the appropriate level of specificity. This process is time-consuming and remains exposed to omissions, documentation ambiguity, interpretive variation, and local workflow constraints. Reviews of discharge coding accuracy have shown substantial variability across settings and code types, reinforcing that coded administrative data are useful but not error-free representations of clinical reality [5]. In this context, AI-assisted coding systems are attractive because they may reduce review burden, prioritize complex cases, and identify clinically documented codes that were missed during an initial human coding pass.

1.2 Automated and computer-assisted coding

Automated clinical coding has been studied for more than two decades. Early systems relied on rules, terminologies, example-based retrieval, and classical natural language processing. A systematic review published in 2010 found that automated coding and classification systems already covered diverse clinical documents and specialties, but also emphasized that performance was highly context-dependent and not easily generalizable [6]. More recent computer-assisted coding (CAC) literature describes potential gains in accuracy, productivity, consistency, and workflow redesign, while stressing the importance of implementation strategy and the evolving role of coding professionals [7].

Academic research has increasingly formulated automatic ICD coding as a large-scale multilabel text classification problem. Public English-language critical care datasets such as MIMIC-III and MIMIC-IV have made reproducible benchmarking possible [8, 9]. On these datasets, successive models have used hierarchical classifiers, convolutional and recurrent networks, label-wise attention, transformer encoders, external code descriptions, and code hierarchy information [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16]. However, the literature also identifies persistent barriers to real-world deployment: long documents, large and imbalanced label spaces, rare codes, evolving guidelines, limited interpretability, and the gap between statistical label prediction and the standard process followed by professional coders [17].

Large language models (LLMs) have renewed interest in medical coding automation, but their role remains unsettled. General-purpose LLMs can produce plausible but incorrect or imprecise codes, and recent work has warned against unvalidated direct use for medical code assignment [18]. Beyond coding itself, LLM-based pipelines have also been used to transform complex free-text clinical narratives into structured criterion-level variables for ICU clinical-trial prescreening; in a 2026 Critical Care study, an LLM workflow applied to ICU discharge summaries achieved a criterion-level F1-score of 0.82 for the best model, a patient-level positive predictive value of 72% after expert review, and an estimated 86% reduction in clinician review time [19]. Current approaches therefore increasingly constrain LLMs with domain-specific fine-tuning, retrieval, reranking, evidence extraction, coding guidelines, repeated or self-consistent inference, and agentic workflows that mimic human coding steps [20, 21, 22]. This evolution is important for PMSI: a useful system must do more than predict a label set. It must structure clinical narratives into auditable evidence, respect coding doctrine, distinguish code roles, handle national coding

specificities, and expose uncertainty for human review.

1.3 Industrial and PMSI-specific landscape

The industrial market reflects the same transition from coding assistance to partial automation. Established CAC and encoder vendors include Solventum/3M Health Information Systems, Optum, Dolbey, TruBridge/TruCode, Microsoft/Nuance, and AGS Health [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28]. A second group of vendors positions products as autonomous or near-autonomous medical coding, including CodaMetrix, Nym, Fathom, XpertDox, Aideo, AKASA, and Semantic Health [29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35]. Cloud and NLP infrastructure providers, such as AWS Comprehend Medical and John Snow Labs Spark NLP for Healthcare, provide terminology linking and clinical entity resolution components that can support coding workflows without necessarily constituting a complete coding system [36, 37].

In France, the PMSI/T2A context has generated a specific market for coding optimization and revenue integrity. The French technical agency ATIH launched a flash survey in 2024 on AI-based PMSI diagnosis coding tools, reflecting institutional interest in the maturity and expectations of this market [38]. Commercial PMSI-oriented actors include SANCARE, Dedalus/SANCARE integrations, Ospi Cod+, Parallel, and CIM-10 search assistants such as cimAi [39, 40, 41, 42, 43]. Public evidence on these systems remains limited, and vendor claims are not a substitute for transparent, protocolized, expert-reviewed evaluation.

1.4 Limitations of single-reference evaluation

Most classification evaluations compare model output with a single reference label set. This is insufficient for clinical coding. A human reference may omit a valid code, select a less specific code, or resolve an ambiguous rule differently from another competent coder. Conversely, a system may propose a code that is syntactically plausible but unsupported by the text or invalid under coding doctrine. Latent-label and multi-annotator methods acknowledge observer error and disagreement [44], but operational evaluation also needs rules that are interpretable to clinicians, coders, and hospital decision-makers.

For AI-assisted coding, the key question is therefore not only whether the system reproduces an initial human coding. It is whether the system proposes codes that are clinically documented, doctrinally acceptable, and useful after expert review. Strict precision remains essential because hallucinated or over-extensive codes create compliance risk. Recall must also be interpreted carefully: if a system proposes a more specific valid code on the same pathology than the human reference, penalizing it for not reproducing the less specific human code would underestimate its value. More generally, patient-safety and quality-improvement research has emphasized that unreliable or incomplete reference processes can lead to overconfident conclusions [45]. Evaluation should therefore combine code-level validity, error typology, semantic recall over a validated superset, valuation impact, and comparison with human inter-expert variability.

1.5 Rationale for NovaT2A evaluation

NovaT2A analyzes stay narratives and administrative metadata to propose PMSI declarations including principal diagnosis, related diagnosis, associated diagnoses, and CCAM procedures. It produces final declared codes, additional candidate codes, textual justifications, and elements used for grouping and valuation. Its evaluation is therefore an evaluation of an assisted coding workflow, not a simple benchmark of label prediction.

At the evaluation level, NovaT2A is a proprietary agentic AI system for the French PMSI setting. Its high-level design combines a reinforcement-learning strategist agent, a symbolic regulatory

layer, an LLM-based clinical interpretation component, and a proxy of the official grouping and valuation function. This architectural combination reflects the structure of the coding problem. Reinforcement learning is suited to sequential decision-making under uncertainty, where the system must decide which hypotheses to explore, which evidence to request, and when a declaration is sufficiently supported. Symbolic AI is suited to PMSI and CCAM regulatory constraints because coding doctrine is rule-heavy, versioned, and must remain auditable. The LLM component is used for evidence-grounded interpretation of clinical text, while avoiding the weaker paradigm of unconstrained direct code generation by a general-purpose model. The grouping proxy connects code hypotheses to the operational object of PMSI coding, namely case-mix grouping and valuation, without claiming to replace the official grouping function.

We designed this study to address the main limitations identified in prior work. First, four experts independently perform blinded primary coding, so that human variability is observable rather than hidden. Second, NovaT2A proposals are reviewed code by code after primary coding is locked, including both final declared codes and additional system-generated candidate codes. Third, adjudication produces a validated code set used to estimate precision, hallucination, semantic recall, and descriptive valuation outputs. Fourth, semantic recall credits valid NovaT2A codes that are at least as complete and on the same clinical topic as a human code, including more specific codes. Finally, Rank from References positions NovaT2A relative to the observed distribution of human expert disagreement rather than treating a single human consensus as an absolute truth [1].

1.6 Objectives

The primary objectives were:

- to measure assisted validated net valuation gain, defined as the best groupable human baseline augmented with expert-validated NovaT2A codes versus the same human baseline alone;

Secondary objectives were:

- to estimate strict precision of evaluable NovaT2A code proposals after expert review;
- to estimate hallucination and non-hallucinatory invalidity rates;
- to estimate semantic recall over the validated superset of human and NovaT2A codes;
- to quantify valid code detection beyond the human consensus;
- to compare NovaT2A with the human expert panel using RFR.

2 Methods

2.1 Study design

We designed a comparative methodological performance study using fictitious hospital stays available in the local NovaT2A repository. The study was non-interventional and conducted on retrospectively available or pre-generated cases, with prospective standardized human annotation for evaluation. The main comparison was between NovaT2A and independent/consensus human coding; the exhaustivity reference was the adjudicated superset of human codes and valid NovaT2A detections; RFR positioned NovaT2A relative to inter-expert variability.

Reporting was informed by TRIPOD+AI, SPIRIT-AI, and CONSORT-AI principles, adapted to a non-interventional methodological performance study rather than a deployed clinical prediction model or clinical trial [46, 47, 48].

2.2 Data source and population

The source material consisted of fictitious hospital stays with completed NovaT2A runs and analyzable stay text. When multiple runs existed for the same stay, the most recent completed run selected by the pre-specified rule was used.

The final analysis dataset contained 44 completed runs with linked stays, 42 deduplicated stays, and 42 selected main runs. All selected runs were processed with NovaT2A version dated 1 May 2026.

2.3 NovaT2A system

NovaT2A was evaluated as the proprietary AI-assisted PMSI coding system version dated 1 May 2026. To preserve intellectual property and reduce misuse risk, this manuscript reports only the functional architecture needed to interpret the evaluation. It does not disclose prompts, model versions, reward functions, regulatory knowledge-base contents, thresholds, ranking policies, or the implementation details of the grouping proxy.

At a high level, NovaT2A combines four interacting components:

- an agentic strategy layer using reinforcement learning to prioritize coding hypotheses, plan evidence checks, and arbitrate between candidate declarations;
- a symbolic regulatory layer representing deterministic PMSI and CCAM constraints, allowing rule-consistent and auditable filtering;
- an LLM-based clinical interpretation component used to support evidence-grounded analysis of the stay text;
- a proxy of the official grouping and valuation function used to estimate the potential grouping consequences of candidate declarations during analysis.

This hybrid design was chosen because PMSI coding is not well represented by a single flat multilabel classifier. It requires sequential exploration, textual evidence extraction, deterministic rule checking, role assignment, and valuation-aware decision support. The evaluated outputs were final declarations, additional candidate codes, citations, justifications, final GHM proxy outputs, and valuation estimates.

2.4 Human annotation

Four experts independently performed blinded primary coding for each stay. They recorded DP, DR when applicable, DAS, CCAM acts, confidence, comments, and supporting citations. A human consensus declaration was then derived from the four primary codings.

2.5 Review and adjudication of NovaT2A proposals

After the primary human coding was locked, each expert reviewed NovaT2A proposals code by code. The review covered both final declared NovaT2A codes and additional system-generated candidate codes. Each proposal was classified as valid, invalid by hallucination, invalid by borderline or overly extensive interpretation, invalid by contested decision rule, indecidable, or not evaluable.

Final adjudication used a three-out-of-four agreement rule when available. Discordant cases were adjudicated by an expert doctrine profile or marked indecidable when no robust adjudication was possible.

2.6 Outcomes

2.6.1 Primary and secondary outcomes

The protocol-defined primary judgment criterion was assisted validated net valuation gain per stay. This outcome was deliberately not an autonomous “NovaT2A alone versus humans” comparison. It measured the value added by expert-validated NovaT2A codes when layered onto a conservative human comparator:

$$GainValid_i = V_i^{NovaValid} - V_i^{HumanInitial}.$$

Here, $V_i^{HumanInitial}$ denotes the human expert valuation baseline. It was defined as the highest groupable valuation obtained after applying the grouping and valuation function to each of the four independent human primary codings. This is conservative because NovaT2A was not compared with a poor isolated human coding, but with the best groupable human primocoding observed among the four experts. If none of the four primary codings could be grouped because the recorded DP was missing or not mapped by the grouping proxy, a groupable baseline was inferred from the expert review decisions: adjudicated-valid NovaT2A DP proposals were tested first, and adjudicated-valid DAS codes were used as DP candidates only when no valid DP proposal yielded a positive grouping value. $V_i^{NovaValid}$ denotes the valuation after augmenting the selected human baseline declaration with NovaT2A codes adjudicated as valid by expert review and recalculating grouping. Therefore, the valuation estimand is “best human plus validated NovaT2A codes” versus “best human alone”, i.e., assisted added value rather than autonomous system performance. For single-role fields such as DP and DR, candidate role assignments available from the selected human baseline and adjudicated valid NovaT2A codes were evaluated with the grouping proxy, and the highest groupable valuation was retained.

Strict precision among evaluable NovaT2A proposals was a secondary performance outcome:

$$PrecisionStrict = \frac{N_{Valid}}{N_{Evaluable}}.$$

The denominator included proposals adjudicated as valid, invalid hallucination, invalid borderline or overly extensive interpretation, and invalid contested rule. Indecidable and not-evaluable proposals were excluded from the strict-precision denominator and summarized separately.

The protocol success thresholds were: a lower 95% confidence bound for mean validated gain strictly above 0 euros for the valuation outcome; and strict precision at least 85% with a lower 95% confidence bound above 75% for the secondary performance outcome. The valuation outcome was measured on all stays after direct or review-informed construction of a groupable human expert baseline. Relative valuation increase was measured as the ratio of the mean validated net gain to the mean human baseline valuation, with paired stay-level bootstrap confidence intervals.

2.6.2 Secondary outcomes

Other secondary outcomes included gross and validated NovaT2A valuation outputs, hallucination rate, non-hallucinatory invalidity, coverage of human consensus codes, validated detection ratio, semantic recall over the validated code superset, inter-expert agreement, and RFR metrics.

2.7 Semantic recall over the validated code superset

The reference superset was defined, within each stay, as the union of human consensus codes and NovaT2A codes adjudicated as valid. Recall was assessed for both NovaT2A and the human consensus.

Exact matches were credited directly. When a human code was not exactly found in NovaT2A, the analysis checked whether NovaT2A had selected a valid code for the same stay that was at least as complete and on the same clinical topic, for example a more specific diagnosis code covering a more general human code. Non-trivial code correspondences were assessed by a local LLM and cached with the reference code, candidate code, relation, confidence, and rationale.

2.8 Rank from References analysis

RFR was used as a variability-aware secondary analysis [1]. Each expert and NovaT2A were represented as binary multilabel matrices over stay by code categories. The four experts formed the reference panel $\chi = \{h_1, \dots, h_4\}$, and NovaT2A was evaluated as the candidate x .

The base distance was Hamming distance:

$$d(x, h_i) = \sum_{j,k} |x_{j,k} - h_{i,j,k}|.$$

We reported the normalized mean distance from references:

$$\Delta_\chi(x) = \frac{1}{mn_d n_c} \sum_{i=1}^m d(x, h_i),$$

the RFR mean rank $\rho_\chi(x)$, the normalized rank $\tilde{\rho}_\chi \in [0, 1]$, and the consensus-proximity percentile $1 - \tilde{\rho}_\chi$.

Non-inferiority was declared if the upper 95% bootstrap confidence bound of NovaT2A $\tilde{\rho}_\chi$ was below the pre-specified human reference quantile of leave-one-expert-out upper confidence bounds. The primary RFR quantile was $q = 0.75$. Bootstrap resampling was performed at the stay level.

2.9 Statistical analysis

Analyses were performed after source-data freeze, completed expert reviews, final adjudication, and locking of derived analysis tables. Proportions were summarized with exact denominators and 95% confidence intervals. Continuous outcomes were summarized by mean, standard deviation, median, interquartile range, and bootstrap confidence intervals. Clustered uncertainty was handled by stay-level bootstrap when appropriate.

The aggregate CSV tables and public R scripts used to reproduce the analysis are available at <https://github.com/ZenoLoi/NovaT2A-Observational-study> [49].

3 Results

3.1 Study population

The source material comprised 44 completed NovaT2A runs linked to stays. After deduplication and selection of one main run per stay, the final analysis population contained 42 fictitious stays. Pre-specified quality checks confirmed complete review by all four experts, complete adjudication of all expected NovaT2A proposals, and non-stale simulation-analysis outputs.

3.2 Primary and secondary outcome status

Assisted validated net valuation gain was measured for all 42 stays after direct or review-informed construction of a groupable human baseline. The estimand compared the best groupable human

Table 1: Corpus description.

Characteristic	Estimate	Notes
Number of stays	42	Deduplicated selected main runs
Age, years	mean 55.8; median 58.5 (IQR 42.2–78.0)	n=42
Stay length	mean 7.4; median 6.0 (IQR 4.0–9.0)	n=40
Text length, characters	mean 54,027; median 21,777 (IQR 18,566–73,230)	n=42
NovaT2A proposals	478	Final declarations plus additional reviewed candidate proposals

baseline plus expert-validated NovaT2A codes with the same human baseline alone. Mean gain was 857.60 euros per stay (95% CI, 416.32 to 1,388.49), corresponding to a 28.2% relative increase over the human baseline (95% CI, 12.2% to 49.4%) and meeting the pre-specified primary success threshold. Strict precision was also measured but did not meet its pre-specified secondary performance threshold: 64.9% (300/462; 95% CI, 60.5% to 69.1%).

Table 2: Primary valuation outcome and selected secondary performance outcome.

Outcome	Protocol estimand	Final result	Success status
Primary valuation outcome	Mean assisted validated net valuation gain per stay: best human plus validated NovaT2A codes versus best human alone, $V^{NovaValid} - V^{HumanInitial}$	+857.60 euros (n=42; 95% CI, +416.32 to +1,388.49); +28.2% relative increase (95% CI, +12.2% to +49.4%)	Met
Secondary performance outcome	Strict precision, $N_{Valid}/N_{Evaluable}$	300/462 = 64.9% (95% CI, 60.5–69.1)	Not met

3.3 Human annotation and inter-expert variability

Primary coding showed substantial variability across domains. Mean pairwise exact agreement was 27.8% for DP, 51.2% for DR, 77.0% for DAS code-presence items, and 49.6% for ACTE code-presence items. Fleiss kappa was 0.221 for DP, 0.164 for DR, 0.033 for DAS, and 0.279 for ACTE. By contrast, the code-by-code review of NovaT2A proposals showed high agreement: all 478 proposals were reviewed by all four experts, mean raw agreement among complete reviews was 92.2%, and Fleiss kappa was 0.746.

3.4 NovaT2A proposal validity

The final analysis included 478 NovaT2A proposals, of which 462 were evaluable for strict precision. Overall, 300 proposals were adjudicated as valid, yielding a strict precision of 64.9% (95% CI, 60.5% to 69.1%). The global error typology among all presented proposals was: invalid hallucination 7/478 (1.5%), invalid borderline interpretation 26/478 (5.4%), invalid contested rule 129/478 (27.0%), indecidable 2/478 (0.4%), and not evaluable 14/478 (2.9%).

Table 3: NovaT2A strict precision and error typology.

Stratum	Presented	Evaluable	Valid	Precision	Halluc.	Rule contested
Global	478	462	300	64.9% (60.5–69.1)	7	129
DP	213	204	128	62.7% (55.9–69.1)	3	62
DR	0	0	0	NA	0	0
DAS	246	239	156	65.3% (59.0–71.0)	4	64
ACTE	19	19	16	84.2% (62.4–94.5)	0	3

Figure 1: Strict precision of NovaT2A proposals by slot.

3.5 Valuation outputs

Each of the four human primary codings was passed through the same grouping and valuation proxy. For each stay, the direct human comparator was the maximum groupable valuation among the four experts. This baseline was intentionally demanding: it avoided measuring NovaT2A against a weak isolated human coding. Mean human baseline valuation was 3,036.78 euros (95% CI, 2,288.85 to 3,890.40; median 2,642.87, IQR 1,770.86–3,001.52).

Gross NovaT2A valuation before expert validation was available for all 42 stays, with a mean of 2,869.49 euros (95% CI, 2,250.48 to 3,686.68; median 2,399.70, IQR 1,616.93–4,072.15). Relative to the complete human baseline, gross gain was negative on average and uncertain: mean -167.29 euros (95% CI, -1,116.64 to 747.59; median 0.00, IQR -821.51–1,063.83).

The assisted NovaT2A valuation was then recalculated by augmenting the selected human baseline declaration with only NovaT2A codes adjudicated valid by the experts. For single-role fields, groupable candidate role assignments from the human baseline and validated NovaT2A codes were evaluated and the highest groupable valuation was retained. This design should be interpreted as an assisted value-added analysis, not as an autonomous NovaT2A declaration replacing human coding. The mean valuation of the augmented declaration was 3,894.38 euros (95% CI, 3,038.33 to 4,901.14; median 2,952.80, IQR 2,156.53–4,072.15; n=42). The resulting mean assisted validated net gain was 857.60 euros (95% CI, 416.32 to 1,388.49; median 0.00, IQR 0.00–931.11; n=42), a 28.2% relative increase over the human baseline (95% CI, 12.2% to 49.4%). Eighteen of 42 validated gains were positive, 24 were zero, and none were negative. This satisfies the pre-specified valuation threshold. Because the corpus is fictitious and the calculation uses a grouping proxy, the monetary magnitude should be confirmed prospectively before operational interpretation.

3.6 GHM specialty distribution

The human baseline GHM and validated NovaT2A GHM were identical in 24/42 stays and belonged to the same CMD-based specialty group in 27/42 stays. Specialty was derived from the first two characters of the GHM code, corresponding to the CMD category. The largest net increases after validated NovaT2A augmentation were observed in hepatobiliary and pancreatic stays (CMD 07, +4), other health-status factors (CMD 23, +3), endocrine/nutrition/metabolism (CMD 10, +2), and infectious/parasitic diseases (CMD 18, +2). Net decreases were observed in nervous system (CMD 01, -3), circulatory system (CMD 05, -3), ENT/oral cavity (CMD 03, -2), and digestive system (CMD 06, -2).

Table 4: Human baseline and validated NovaT2A GHM distributions by CMD-based medical specialty. Counts are stays; values in parentheses are counts for each GHM.

Medical specialty	Human baseline GHM	Validated NovaT2A GHM
CMD 01: Nervous system	7: 01M35Z (6); 01M35T (1)	4: 01M35Z (3); 01M35T (1)
CMD 02: Eye	1: 02M081 (1)	0
CMD 03: ENT and oral cavity	2: 03M15T (1); 03M15Z (1)	0
CMD 04: Respiratory system	2: 04M23Z (2)	3: 04M23Z (3)
CMD 05: Circulatory system	3: 05M171 (2); 05M17T (1)	0
CMD 06: Digestive system	3: 06M091 (2); 06M092 (1)	1: 06M093 (1)
CMD 07: Hepatobiliary and pancreas	1: 07M041 (1)	5: 07M042 (2); 07M043 (2); 07M044 (1)
CMD 08: Musculoskeletal/connective tissue	0	1: 08M36T (1)
CMD 09: Skin, subcutaneous tissue, breast	1: 09M14Z (1)	0
CMD 10: Endocrine, nutrition, metabolism	1: 10M14Z (1)	3: 10M14Z (3)
CMD 11: Kidney and urinary tract	2: 11M19Z (2)	2: 11M19Z (2)
CMD 12: Male genital system	1: 12M09Z (1)	1: 12M09Z (1)
CMD 13: Female genital system	1: 13M10Z (1)	0
CMD 16: Blood and immunology	4: 16M15Z (4)	3: 16M15Z (3)
CMD 17: Myeloproliferative/neoplastic disorders	2: 17M172 (1); 17M173 (1)	2: 17M173 (2)
CMD 18: Infectious and parasitic diseases	2: 18M14Z (2)	4: 18M14Z (4)
CMD 19: Mental disorders	1: 19M22Z (1)	2: 19M22Z (2)
CMD 21: Injuries, poisoning, toxic effects	4: 21M141 (2); 21M142 (2)	4: 21M141 (2); 21M142 (2)
CMD 23: Other health-status factors	4: 23M20Z (4)	7: 23M20Z (7)

3.7 Exhaustivity and semantic recall

The validated superset contained 391 reference code items: 93 with human origin and 300 with NovaT2A-valid origin. Exact recall was 76.7% for NovaT2A and 23.8% for the human consensus. Semantic recall, which credited codes on the same clinical topic that were at least as complete as the reference code, was 80.8% for NovaT2A and 28.9% for the human consensus. The large gap mainly reflected validated NovaT2A-associated diagnoses that were absent from the human consensus. Human-code coverage by NovaT2A final declarations remained low: 2/93 (2.2%) for final declarations and 4/93 (4.3%) for wider tested or eligible coverage. The ratio of adjudicated valid NovaT2A codes to human consensus codes was 3.23 globally.

Table 5: Semantic recall over the validated code superset.

Stratum	Superset	Human sem.	NovaT2A sem.	Human exact	NovaT2A exact
Global	391	28.9%	80.8%	23.8%	76.7%
DP	167	30.5%	83.2%	24.6%	76.6%
DR	29	100.0%	17.2%	100.0%	0.0%
DAS	158	7.6%	98.7%	1.3%	98.7%
ACTE	37	56.8%	43.2%	56.8%	43.2%

The semantic matching step was intended to avoid penalizing a valid, more specific NovaT2A code when it covered the same pathology as a less specific human code. For example, a more specific biliary diagnosis such as calculus of the gallbladder with acute cholecystitis can cover a less specific human cholecystitis code when both refer to the same documented pathology and the NovaT2A code is adjudicated valid.

3.8 RFR analysis

RFR positioned NovaT2A relative to the distribution of the four human experts. Globally, NovaT2A had $\Delta_x = 0.0193$ (95% CI, 0.0155 to 0.0237), $\tilde{\rho}_x = 0.915$ (95% CI, 0.861 to 0.959), and

a consensus-proximity percentile of 8.5%. The pre-specified non-inferiority criterion was not met globally. Stated plainly, NovaT2A was very far from the expert panel. This is partly expected for an exhaustivity-oriented system that proposes many additional adjudicated valid codes rather than reproducing the initial human coding distribution, but it is also a signal of non-alignment with expert coding practice. Stratified analysis showed the same pattern for role-exact diagnostics, role-ignored diagnostics, DP, DAS, and ACTE. The DR stratum was the only stratum in which NovaT2A met both non-inferiority and superiority criteria; however, this occurred in a setting where no NovaT2A DR proposal was adjudicated valid, so the result should be interpreted as low divergence rather than evidence of strong DR detection.

Table 6: Rank from References analysis.

Stratum	Δ_χ	$\tilde{\rho}_\chi$	Consensus perc.	Non-inf.	Superior
Global	0.0193	0.915	8.5%	No	No
Diagnostics, role exact	0.0210	0.957	4.3%	No	No
Diagnostics, role ignored	0.0216	0.919	8.1%	No	No
DP	0.0210	0.861	13.9%	No	No
DR	0.0071	0.345	65.5%	Yes	Yes
DAS	0.0256	0.956	4.4%	No	No
ACTE	0.0123	0.523	47.7%	No	No

Figure 2: Horizontal violin distributions of global code-level normalized Rank from References results by participant. Each violin aggregates $\tilde{\rho}_\chi$ values across codes; black points show the aggregate estimate. Higher $\tilde{\rho}_\chi$ indicates greater distance from the reference expert panel.

4 Discussion

4.1 Principal findings

In this comparative methodological evaluation on 42 fictitious PMSI stays, NovaT2A generated 478 reviewed proposals from its standard proposal set. The pre-specified valuation threshold was met for the assisted value-added estimand: best groupable human baseline plus expert-validated NovaT2A codes versus the same human baseline alone. Mean assisted validated net gain was 857.60 euros per stay across all 42 stays, with a lower 95% confidence bound above 0 euros, corresponding to a 28.2% relative increase over the human baseline (95% CI, 12.2% to

49.4%). This result should not be read as NovaT2A-alone valuation superiority over humans. The pre-specified secondary strict-precision threshold was not met: strict precision among evaluable proposals was 64.9%, below the success threshold, with a low adjudicated hallucination rate of 1.5%. NovaT2A semantic recall over the validated code superset was higher than the human consensus recall (80.8% versus 28.9%), reflecting many adjudicated valid NovaT2A-associated codes absent from the human consensus. RFR did not support global non-inferiority relative to the human expert panel: NovaT2A remained far from the expert distribution, consistent with a system designed to expand declarative exhaustivity rather than to imitate human primary coding.

4.2 Interpretation

The evaluation separates three questions that are often conflated: whether NovaT2A proposals are valid after expert review, whether they increase exhaustivity over a validated code superset, and whether the overall pattern of coding differs from experts more than experts differ from each other. This is especially important when human primary coding is not an absolute gold standard. On this corpus, NovaT2A behaved primarily as a high-recall proposal-generation system. The fact that it proposes something very different from humans is therefore not surprising: its purpose is not to reproduce current human coding practice, but to substantially increase the exhaustivity of the candidate declaration submitted to expert verification. Its low hallucination count is encouraging, but the large number of rule-contested or borderline invalid proposals means that expert review remains central to any compliance-sensitive workflow.

The divergence between high semantic recall and unfavorable global RFR is informative rather than contradictory. Semantic recall rewards the system for covering the validated superset; RFR penalizes global distance from how human experts distribute codes across stays and roles. In this setting, a high global RFR distance partly reflects expansion of the candidate code space beyond ordinary human primocoding. However, it should not be treated as a benign technical artifact. A system that repeatedly proposes a distribution of codes far from expert practice could induce a doctrine shift if its outputs were adopted at scale, especially in a reimbursement-sensitive environment. This reinforces two points at once: the intended use case is not human mimicry but aggressive exhaustivity support followed by expert selection, and this exhaustivity-oriented behavior must be bounded by explicit doctrine governance.

4.3 Scientific and societal impact

This study reframes the evaluation of AI-assisted hospital coding. Instead of asking whether NovaT2A merely reproduces a single human reference, it evaluates whether the system surfaces additional codes that remain valid after expert review. Scientifically, the work combines blinded multi-expert primary coding, adjudicated proposal review, semantic recall over a validated code superset, valuation analysis, and Rank from References benchmarking against inter-expert variability. This provides a more realistic framework for coding tasks in which the human reference can itself be incomplete.

For clinical and operational readers, PMSI coding turns clinical narratives into standardized diagnosis and procedure codes that influence case-mix description and activity-based payment. Manual coding is expert work, but it can miss valid information and experts may disagree. The societal impact is therefore tied to declarative exhaustivity. More complete PMSI coding can improve the description of hospital activity, support fairer resource allocation, and reduce missed documentation value, provided that compliance risk is controlled. In the present corpus, the mean assisted validated net valuation gain was 857.60 euros per stay, corresponding to a 28.2% relative increase over the human baseline. This value represents additional expert-validated codes layered onto the best groupable human baseline, not autonomous AI replacement of human cod-

ing. This stay-level magnitude should not be extrapolated directly to national finances because the corpus is fictitious and not prevalence-weighted, but it shows why even small changes in coding exhaustivity can be economically material when applied to a national activity-based payment system. The results support a coder-in-the-loop model: NovaT2A expands the candidate declaration space, while human experts retain responsibility for final acceptance, rule interpretation, and institutional accountability.

4.4 Market and payer implications

The following market and payer implications should be read as conjectures rather than demonstrated effects. The empirical basis remains limited: 42 fictitious stays, a single NovaT2A version, an expert panel and evaluation workflow organized in the Nova Medicae context, and valuation estimates produced through a grouping proxy that is not publicly auditable. These hypotheses are therefore intended to frame questions for confirmation or refutation in a large-scale clinical study planned for late 2026.

Under this conjectural scenario, the economic interpretation would not be limited to hospital revenue capture. If a high-exhaustivity coding technology were deployed only in a subset of establishments, equipped hospitals might obtain more complete reimbursable declarations than non-equipped hospitals for comparable clinical activity. Such an effect would not necessarily reflect better care, higher case complexity, or greater underlying resource use; it could instead reflect unequal access to coding technology. Partial deployment could therefore create a market effect by favoring equipped establishments, widening differences between hospitals with similar activity, and increasing pressure on a regulated national envelope.

This conjecture also creates a potential dual interest for the Caisse nationale de l'Assurance maladie (CNAM). On one hand, better coding exhaustivity could make activity description more faithful and reduce under-recognition of documented care, which is relevant for fair allocation of resources. On the other hand, payer oversight would need to distinguish legitimate correction of undercoding from systematic over-extension, rule-contested coding, shifts driven by vendor-specific behavior, and broader shifts in coding doctrine. The unfavorable global RFR result is relevant here: it suggests that high-exhaustivity AI assistance can produce a coding distribution that is far from expert practice, even when many additional codes are valid after review. A national payer could benefit from nationally specified audit logs, comparable performance metrics, targeted audit signals, and reproducible expert-reviewed benchmarks that identify where additional value reflects documented valid codes rather than unsupported optimization, but this remains a policy hypothesis pending clinical-scale evidence.

These considerations suggest, rather than prove, the need to define a national standard for AI-assisted PMSI coding technologies before broad but incomplete coverage of the hospital sector. Such a standard would not prescribe a single product architecture or force vendors into one implementation. It should instead define the common evaluation and governance requirements that any technology would have to satisfy: independent evaluation on representative real-world stays, explicit human-in-the-loop governance, shared definitions of valid proposal, hallucination, borderline invalidity, and contested-rule invalidity, version-locked performance reporting, auditability of evidence shown to coders, and post-deployment monitoring of valuation drift by specialty, hospital type, and vendor. Because non-alignment with expert practice can become a doctrine-shift risk when embedded into routine coding workflows, this governance should be framed with payer and national digital-health and PMSI institutions, including ATIH, ANS, and CNAM. Without such a standard, adoption could hypothetically become a competitive advantage based on access to coding technology rather than a nationally controlled improvement in documentation quality and payment fairness.

4.5 Comparison with existing evaluation approaches

Single-reference precision and recall are insufficient when reference coders may miss valid codes. The semantic superset recall and RFR analyses complement strict precision by allowing validated added detections and by benchmarking NovaT2A against human variability rather than against a unique consensus.

4.6 Strengths

- Blinded independent primary coding by four experts.
- Code-by-code expert review of NovaT2A final declarations and additional candidate codes.
- Separation of hallucination, borderline invalidity, and contested-rule invalidity.
- Validated-code superset recall to avoid penalizing more precise valid NovaT2A codes.
- RFR-based expert-relative analysis with stay-level bootstrap.
- NovaT2A includes a native, user-friendly rule editor intended to support continuous doctrine alignment in deployment. This makes local expert alignment iterative: a contested eligibility rule can be adjusted once for a given code and then revisited only when a subsequent regulatory change specifically affects that rule.

4.7 Limitations

- The corpus consists of fictitious stays and may not cover the full complexity of real MCO records.
- The market, payer, and national-standard implications are conjectural because they are based on 42 fictitious stays, one NovaT2A version, an expert panel and evaluation workflow organized in the Nova Medicae context, and a proprietary grouping proxy that was not independently audited.
- Human expert reviews are themselves subject to variability.
- RFR depends on the quality and diversity of the human panel.
- Results apply to the NovaT2A version dated 1 May 2026 and may not generalize to other NovaT2A versions, LLM versions, or PMSI referentials.
- The valuation design measured assisted added value: best groupable human baseline plus expert-validated NovaT2A codes versus best groupable human baseline alone. It does not estimate autonomous NovaT2A performance as a replacement for human coding, and the selected human baseline may differ from how a real institutional consensus would be finalized.
- Rule-contested false positives are not harmless operationally. Even when they are caught by expert review, they can consume cognitive workload in coding teams and may reduce usability if the local doctrine-alignment process is not efficient.
- The review process evaluated the proposal set surfaced by NovaT2A; it does not quantify the value or risk of candidates not surfaced to expert review.

4.8 Implications

These findings support a deployment model in which NovaT2A is used to surface candidate codes for expert verification rather than to autonomously finalize PMSI declarations. The low hallucination rate suggests that the reviewed proposal pool can be clinically informative, while the

rule-contested category highlights the need for doctrine-aware review and conservative acceptance thresholds. Future evaluations should include real-world cases, prospectively valued human comparator declarations, prospective timing and productivity measures, independent expert panels, payer-oriented audit metrics, and prospective monitoring of distributional effects across establishments. A large-scale clinical evaluation planned for late 2026 is intended to confirm or refute the market, payer, valuation, and governance hypotheses raised by this methodological study. If confirmed, these elements should feed a national standard for evaluating and governing AI-assisted PMSI coding technologies. RFR should be retained as a complementary analysis because it distinguishes added exhaustivity from expert-like coding behavior.

5 Conclusion

On a fictitious PMSI corpus, NovaT2A version dated 1 May 2026 achieved a positive assisted validated net valuation gain when expert-validated NovaT2A codes were added to the best groupable human baseline (+857.60 euros per stay; +28.2% relative increase), 64.9% strict precision among evaluable proposals, and 80.8% semantic recall over the validated code superset, with a 1.5% hallucination rate. The primary valuation threshold was met, but the secondary strict-precision threshold was not. These results indicate substantial potential for expert-reviewed exhaustivity support, but they do not establish global expert-equivalent coding behavior or autonomous AI coding superiority over humans. NovaT2A should therefore be interpreted as a coder-in-the-loop decision-support system pending prospective validation with real-world comparator valuation.

Ethics and governance

The study used fictitious stays from a demonstration corpus and did not involve real patients, care delivery, clinical decision-making, or access to identifiable patient data. The analysis was conducted as a methodological evaluation of an AI-assisted coding system. Before any public dissemination of source documents, the corpus should remain subject to internal confidentiality and intellectual-property review.

Data availability

The minimal aggregate CSV tables needed to reproduce the numerical results reported in this manuscript are available in the GitHub repository *NovaT2A-Observationnal-study* [49]. The public data package contains aggregate, non-patient-level outputs only. Individual stay texts, source documents, row-level code proposals, adjudication rationales, and proprietary NovaT2A internals are not publicly distributed.

Code availability

Public R scripts that read the aggregate CSV tables and reproduce the analysis are available in the same GitHub repository [49]. Manuscript-generation scripts, the NovaT2A application, internal prompts, reward functions, regulatory knowledge base, model configuration, and grouping proxy implementation are proprietary and are not released. The evaluated NovaT2A version is dated 1 May 2026.

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Competing interests

All authors are affiliated with Nova Medicae, the company developing NovaT2A. Zeno Loi is medical director of Nova Medicae, Hugo Loi is chief executive officer, and Seymour Loi and Victor Loi are board members. These roles constitute competing interests for the evaluation of NovaT2A. The evaluation design therefore emphasizes blinded primary coding by four experts, code-by-code review of NovaT2A proposals, adjudication, semantic recall over a validated code superset, and Rank from References benchmarking against human expert variability.

Author contributions

Zeno Loi: conceptualization, methodology, clinical coding framework, software supervision, analysis, writing – original draft, and writing – review and editing. Hugo Loi: project administration, resources, software supervision, and writing – review and editing. Seymour Loi: governance, resources, and writing – review and editing. Victor Loi: governance, resources, and writing – review and editing. All authors approved the final preprint draft.

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